

Reproducibility and reliability of renal image segmentation and radiomics: the AI4PKD project

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GNB 2025 – June 16-18 2025 – Palermo, Italy

BACKGROUND

- **Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease (ADPKD)** is characterized by multiple fluid-filled cysts in the kidneys and often the liver, which lead to chronic kidney injury [1].
- Total kidney volume and cyst volume currently represent the most relevant biomarkers to monitor disease progression, to assess response to therapy, and for prognosis.
- Besides, non-cystic renal parenchyma volume may provide additional relevant information about the presence of peritubular interstitial fibrosis, associated with renal function and its decline over time [1].
- **Multi-parametric MRI (mp-MRI)**, combining morphological and diffusion MRI, can quantify kidney and liver cysts, as well characterize the non-cystic component through the extraction of radiomic features.
- A **fully automatic segmentation method** to detect kidneys, liver and cysts in ADPKD patients able to exploit the multi-parametric information provided by anatomical and diffusion MRI would be desirable, but not fully available yet in the literature.

AIM

Project **AI4PKD** aims to discover novel MRI-based biomarkers that identify ADPKD stage, based on robust and reliable AI-based methods for the automatic analysis of abdominal mp-MRI images of ADPKD patients.

In the first part of the project, activities focused on developing tools that guarantee reproducibility and reliability of the outcomes:

1. Quantification of the impact of *segmentation* and *scan-rescan* variability on radiomics reproducibility using T2-weighted MRI scans of kidneys.
2. Assessment of the reliability of radiomic features extracted from anatomical and diffusion MRI images of ADPKD patients.

These two activities allowed to identify the best setting, to ensure robustness and reliability of the analyses for the extraction of biomarkers.

SEGMENTATION & SCAN-RESCAN REPRODUCIBILITY

DATASET

- T2-weighted coronal kidney MRI scans of 30 with Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) and 30 Healthy Controls (HC) from a public repository [2] along with manually segmented ground truth masks (GT).
- 10 subjects (5 CKD, 5 HC, 650 2D slices), scanned 5 times within a single session, used as test data and for the radiomic analysis.
- 50 subjects (25 CKD, 25 HC, 649 2D slices), scanned once, used for the training of the models (80% training, 20% validation), together with the.

NETWORK ARCHITECTURES

- **Deterministic U-Net:** 2D U-Net of [2].
- **U-Net with Uncertainty Estimation:**
 - Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) [3].
 - Test-Time Augmentation (TTA) [4].

ROIS & RADIOMIC FEATURES EXTRACTION

- Ground Truth (**GT**) mask manually segmented.
- Deterministic Prediction (**DP**) mask from the deterministic U-Net.
- Masks with different segmentation Confidence Levels (**CL**), with thresholds *th* for agreement among the 50 MCD or TTA predictions.
- 105 radiomic features extracted using Pyradiomics from GT, DP and CL masks for all test acquisitions.

REPRODUCIBILITY ANALYSIS

- Reproducibility to segmentation variability assessed by Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) type 3 between manually and automatically kidney regions (ICC_A).
- Reproducibility to scan-rescan variability assessed by ICC type 2 among the 5 scan repetitions per subject (ICC_S).
- Analysis with and without uncertainty information, and for CKDs and HCs separately.
- Features

	$ICC_A \geq 0.8$	$ICC_S \geq 0.8$	classified
$ICC_A \geq 0.8$	Class 1	Class 2	
$ICC_S < 0.8$	Class 3	Class 4	

REPRODUCIBILITY RESULTS

- For all methods and patients, the n° of features in class 4 decreases as *th* increases, while the n° of features in class 3 increases, up to an optimal *th_{opt}* (circled in figure).
- For HCs subjects, the n° of features in class 1 increases too.
- As *th* increases, more internal kidney regions are selected as ROIs.
- TTA predictions show greater variability, as increasing *th* leads to smaller ROIs identified.

(A) Workflow for ROIs definition. Reproducibility analysis without (B) and with (C) segmentation uncertainty information.

RELIABILITY OF RADIOMIC FEATURES

DATASET

14 ADPKD patients from EuroCYST initiative (Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri). T1-w, T2-w, and DWI scans without contrast media (CRISP protocol [5]) with *b*-values = 0, 15, 50, 100, 200, 350, 500, 700, 1000 *s/mm*².

METHODS

IVIM parametric maps (*D*, *f*, and *D**) obtained from DWI images using a fully connected neural network [6].

1. Non-cystic tissue identified using manual Ground Truth (GT) and a Deep Learning Network for identifying cysts [7] on T2-weighted images: non-cystic region obtained by subtracting the cystic tissue from the total kidney volume (DL_{start}).
2. Post-processed version (DL_{adj}) created by removing vessels, fat, and hemorrhagic cysts with mp-MRI.

92 radiomics features were extracted from each image and segmentation, considering the two kidney separately.

Radiomic feature reliability was assessed using ICC across different non-cystic segmentations:

- reproducible: $ICC > 0.8$ between regions of interest (ROIs) with similar information content (GT and DL_{adj});
- Informative: $ICC < 0.5$ between ROIs with different content (GT and DL_{start}).

The percentage of reliable features for each image type was determined.

RESULTS

- DL_{adj} segmentation closer to the GT compared to the DL_{start} .
- Dice scores revealed a stronger agreement between DL_{adj} and GT (0.69 ± 0.08) compared to DL_{start} and GT (0.51 ± 0.11).
- Radiomic reliability is higher for DL_{adj} segmentation for IVIM maps ($ICC > 0.8$).
- DL_{adj} exhibited lower reproducibility for T1-w and T2-w images, while DL_{start} demonstrated higher ICC values for these images.

		GT	DL_{start}	DL_{adj}
<i>f</i>	GT	1.00	0.28	0.86
	DL_{start}	0.28	1.00	0.28
	DL_{adj}	0.86	0.28	1.00
<i>D</i>	GT	1.00	0.26	0.81
	DL_{start}	0.26	1.00	0.30
	DL_{adj}	0.81	0.30	1.00
<i>D*</i>	GT	1.00	0.41	0.89
	DL_{start}	0.41	1.00	0.43
	DL_{adj}	0.89	0.43	1.00
T2-w	GT	1.00	0.61	0.49
	DL_{start}	0.61	1.00	0.69
	DL_{adj}	0.49	0.69	1.00
T1-w	GT	1.00	0.70	0.51
	DL_{start}	0.70	1.00	0.40
	DL_{adj}	0.51	0.40	1.00

The percentage of reliable features for each image, grouped by radiomic feature classes, shows FO and GLCM for *D* and *f* parametric maps as the most reliable features, with T1-w and T2-w images showing lower reliability.

FO: First Order; GLCM: Gray-Level Co-Occurrence Matrix; GLDM: Gray-Level Dependence Matrix; GLRLM: Gray-Level Run Length Matrix; GLSZM: Gray-Level Size Zone Matrix; NGTDM: Neighbouring Gray Tone Difference Matrix

CONCLUSIONS

Results show the possibility of **guaranteeing reproducibility and reliability of automatic segmentation tools and radiomic analysis pipelines**, which can support the potential diffusion of imaging for ADPKD characterization in the clinical field.

The small sample size could limit the generalizability of the results.

More images will be considered in the future to increase the sample size and generalize the results.

REFERENCES

1. Caroli, et al., "Intermediate volume on computed tomography imaging defines a fibrotic compartment that predicts glomerular filtration rate decline in autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease patients", The American Journal of Pathology 179, 619-627 (2011)
2. Daniel et al., "Automated renal segmentation in healthy and chronic kidney disease subjects using a convolutional neural network," Magn Reson Med 86(2), 1125-1136 (2021)
3. Gal and Ghahramani, "Dropout as a Bayesian approximation: representing model uncertainty in deep learning," International Conference on Machine Learning, PMLR (2016)
4. Wang et al., "Aleatoric uncertainty estimation with test-time augmentation for medical image segmentation with convolutional neural networks", Neurocomputing 338, 34-45 (2019)
5. Chapman et al., "Renal structure in early autosomal-dominant polycystic kidney disease (ADPKD): the consortium for radiologic imaging studies of polycystic kidney disease (CRISP) cohort," Kidney International 64(3), 1035-1045 (2003)
6. Mastropietro et al., "A supervised deep neural network approach with standardized targets for enhanced accuracy of IVIM parameter estimation from multi-SNR images", NMR in Biomedicine 35(10), e4774 (2022)
7. Kline et al., "Automatic semantic segmentation of kidney cysts in MR images of patients affected by autosomal-dominant polycystic kidney disease", Abdominal Radiology 46, 1053-1061 (2021)

FUNDINGS

This work was supported by the Italian Ministry of University and Research, grant protocol number 2022B23JT5, CUP B53D23002480006, call PRIN 2022 (DD MUR n. 104, 02.02.2022), funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU (PNRR M4.C2.1.1), project title "AI-based methods to improve stratification of patients affected by Polycystic Kidney Disease using multi-parametric MRI – AI4PKD".

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